

RELATIONSHIPS OF KINDNESS

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Cooked Illustrations

This leaflet is for you.

Think of it as an invitation to take fifteen minutes to yourself.

Here you will find various creative activities and relaxing games designed to help you discover, or re-discover, places in your environment that bring you a sense of wellbeing.

It could be as simple as going out in the fresh air...

Follow in step-by-step, or go to a random page. All we ask is that you give some of these exercises a try.

...or even just discovering something that makes you smile.

...talking to a friend over your favourite drink...

Sensory Activities

Going outside for even five minutes can help ground us and make us feel better, no matter the weather!

Try stepping outside for this sensory activity.

Eat a little piece of food. A snack or a spoonful of a meal.

Eat it slowly.

Enjoy the flavour,

focus on the texture.

Think of three words to describe the taste.

Close your eyes, Take three deep breaths. What can you smell?

Notice how the weather affects the scents (rain, for example).

Look into the distance for ten breaths. Now observe the midground for another ten breaths.

Now look around the space you are in for ten breaths.

What's the furthest point you can focus on?

Are any objects in the room you work in the same as any objects outside?

Did you notice something you have never noticed before?

Close your eyes and simply focus on what you can hear for as long as you want.

What sounds do you focus on over others?

Did you pick up on any sounds you were not aware of?

Turn your neck from side to side.

Look up, look to the right, look to the left.

Roll your shoulders and relax your jaw.

Notice how you feel physically, how your body feels.

What sensations or tactile feelings do you observe?

Mindful Doodling

Doodling is a great way to let your mind relax and keep your hand active. Here are some simple exercises you can do in the box below, or on a separate piece of paper if you'd prefer.

 Draw patterns that reflect how you feel. An upbeat swirl for joy, a jagged line for energetic, etc. Make it your own. This is all about being expressive.

 Blind drawing. Just close your eyes and make some lines on the paper. Be mindful of how the pen or pencil moves on the paper.

Haiku

A haiku is a short poem that captures an image or moment, traditionally in 3 lines with a 5-7-5 syllable pattern.

Try writing your own haiku.

*Autumn moonlight -
the worm digs silently
into the chestnut.*

Matsuo Basho (1644-1694)

Collaging with Nature

Let's turn our feelings of gratitude into something that lasts.

Either alone or as a group, find some stones. Write on each one something that you genuinely feel lucky to have in your life.

Think about some other creative collages you can make outside using found materials.

They can be as artistic or as silly as you like!

Why not go with a colleague to visit your collages as the seasons change?

Observe how time passing has affected your work.

Think about arranging the stones in creative ways outside for others to see.

Leave these somewhere outside your workplace.

How to make an upcycled terrarium

We know that spending just five minutes outdoors can improve our mood and wellbeing. And research suggests that just the sight of greenery indoors can have beneficial effects on how we feel. So, why not **add some greenery** to your workspace?

Better yet, why not **make your own living desktop garden** by making a terrarium?

Open terraria are better for cacti and succulents. Humid environments with a tightly closed lid are better for mosses or air plants.

What You'll Need

Small stones or pebbles: for the base layer, to help drainage.

Soil: you only need a handful

Plants!

Activated charcoal: avoids growth of unwanted bacteria

A selection of small tools: pencil/chopstick, little trowels, long spoons will do.

Decoration: Anything you like!

Making your terrarium

- In your clean and dry container, layer up your pebbles to about 2-3cm.
- Scatter the charcoal over the pebbles.
- Layer on the potting soil. Ensure there is enough, so the plant roots sit comfortably deep inside it.
- Your biggest plant or seed goes in first. Gently place the plant into the soil. You can use a pencil-like tool to fill in and flatten the soil around it.
- Make sure your plant has enough room to grow a little; don't cramp them against the glass.
- Place in other stones, or maybe some moss or sand to cover up the soil. Exposed soil is sad soil.
- Put in any finishing decorations on the glass or inside the terrarium.
- Close the lid – or don't!

Choose a spot with plenty of natural light (but not in direct sunlight).

Spray your terrarium with water every couple of weeks; or when the soil is dry to the touch.

Bring the outdoors in

There are many other ways to connect with the outdoors while working inside your building. Here are some ideas.

Nourish your body.

We are what we eat!
Ensure your diet is
colourful and nutritious.
We can't feel happy if
our plates look sad.

Touch some
textured rocks.

Is there a place you have
attached a memory to?
Take a stone or pebble
from that place and keep
it in your pocket.

Touch it and return
to a happy memory.

Smell some herbs!

Nature has so many beautiful scents!
Try keeping a sprig of basil in your
pocket or a potted mint plant on
your desk to remind you of the
outside world.

Plant some visual cues!

A potted plant brings joy to any space! Put it on your desk as a daily reminder of nature.

The plant can even be artificial if you're not green-fingered!

Alternatively, keep a photo on your desk of a place that brings you peace and well-being.

It's very important not to lose sight of what lies outside. Maintaining a connection with nature can help ground us and make us feel better.

Tend to your mind!

There's only one of you! Look after yourself. Take the time to check in and see how you're really feeling.

If your head is full of worries, try to do something with your hands to distract yourself.

You will thank yourself later.

Gratitude!

Is there someone you are grateful to work with?

Think of a short sentence to say to them that would bring a little sunshine into their day.

Share the message with your colleague! Use a post-it note, email it, or say it to them.

We hope you found this booklet of mindfulness activities useful.

Refer to these pages again if you ever need to to take a short break to just breathe.

What happens now?

There is a new initiative in the Health Board. Staff will be able to adopt a planter or small green outdoor area to care for and plant in, with support from the gardening team.

If you want to be involved in this initiative, or if you would like to be added to a mailing list of like-minded people involved across our hospital locations, email our Arts and Health Coordinator.

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